

Study of human and animal Interaction-mini review

Mehwish Altaf^{1*}

1. Department of Zoology, Wildlife and Fisheries, PMAS-Arid Agriculture University Rawalpindi, Pakistan

*Corresponding author e-mail: mehwishabbasi1994.ma@gmail.com

SUMMARY

The affiliation between fauna and human beings many years ago and societies all around the worldwide has evolved methods of winning with their local creature over era. Human used animal in traditional medicine, religion, poetry, omens, food, folklores, entertainment, culture, calligraphy, and art. Petting, loving, and playing with pet animal species; it can be comforting, maintain heart beat, stroke, and physically beneficial. Review of bioindicators and plankton are as potential to be employed as bioindicator for quality of water evaluation and products. Scavengers are used for the elimination of dead animals so that diseases do not propagate to other animals and recycling of nutrients. Predators also play beneficial role in ecology by not only limit the development of potential epizootics but improvement of genetic diversity among herbivore communities.

Keyword: Zoonotic Diseases, Animal, Human, Biological indicators, Ethnomedicine

Citation: Altaf, M. 2022. Study of human and animal Interaction-mini review. International Journal of Forest Sciences. 2: 58-64.

INTRODUCTION

The affiliation between fauna and human beings hundreds of years ago, and civilizations all in earth has evolved distinguishing methods of winning with their local creature over era (Anthony and Wasambo, 2009; Liu *et al.*, 2011; Bowen-Jones, 2012). As a part of the animals that inhabits the planet, we engaged with the creatures around human during our time together, establishing numerous reciprocal interactions since our species' beginnings (Haider *et al.*, 2017; Hakeem *et al.*, 2017; Rauf *et al.*, 2017; Altaf, 2018; Altaf *et al.*, 2018; Adil *et al.*, 2019; Kanwal *et al.*, 2019; Ijaz *et al.*, 2020; Noor and Haider, 2020). The utilize of animals and animal parts to restore to health of human with various health problems has a long olden times and remains accepted in many regions of earth, even when medical art is at its peak (Aslam and Faiz, 2020; Ijaz *et al.*, 2020; Mughal *et al.*, 2020; Ijaz and Iftikhar, 2021; Saleem *et al.*, 2021; Saeed *et al.*, 2022; Umair *et al.*, 2022).

Animal are very important, because they are used scientifically, educationally, economically, culturally, biological indicator, biological control, and aesthetically. Human used animal in traditional medicine, religion, poetry, omens, food, folklores, entertainment, culture, calligraphy, and art (Benítez, 2011; Yirga *et al.*, 2011; Alves *et al.*, 2013; Sreekeesoon and Mahomoodally, 2014; Vijayakumar *et al.*, 2015;

Muhammad *et al.*, 2017a; Muhammad *et al.*, 2017b; Muhammad *et al.*, 2017c; Nijman and Shepherd, 2017). The wild animals are important for sustainable ecosystem. They are significant for ecology as a seed dispersers, pollinators, and recycling of nutrients. Meat is used as a food source. Humans have used meat as a food from the origin. Because it is known as a significant source of vitamins, iron, minerals and especially proteins. Meat has good flavor and taste; beneficial for human health; and has essential amino acids. million years. High rate of pet ownership is seen past societies. Petting, loving, and playing with pet animal species; it can be comforting, maintain heart beat, stroke, and physically beneficial. However, human interaction and affiliation is decreasing with passage of time, human interaction is rapidly shifting toward industrialization. Animal viz. amphibian, reptiles, fishes, mammals, and birds are used for meat and products (Haidar and Bashir, 2021). Different parts of animals are used treat multiple diseases from the origin of human. Wildlife plays an important role; human interactions with wildlife can be transferred pathogens to people (EHS, 2016a, b; Kazwala, 2016; Shiferaw *et al.*, 2017; Botelho *et al.*, 2018; da Silva *et al.*, 2018; Altaf, 2020; Ye *et al.*, 2020).

ANIMALS AS BIOINDICATORS

Bioindicators are live species such as invertebrates, plants, reptiles, mammals, and birds and these are utilized to know the ecosystem health, to analyze “biogeographic changes” and “environmental health” in the environment (Burger, 2006a, b; Holt and Miller, 2011). All organisms within a ecological system gives knowledge about surrounds health, like plankton, which respond rapidly to alternations in the environment and works as a noteworthy biomarker for supervising an indicator of water contamination and quality of water (Pradhan *et al.*, 2008; Thakur *et al.*, 2013). Small creature, which functions as an early caution indication, also best reproduces the health of water vegetation. We attempted to describe the idea of bioindicators and plankton in this review, with a focus on its possible to be employed as biological indicators for quality of water estimation and products (Sidra *et al.*, 2019; Babar and Kanwal, 2021).

ECOLOGICAL ROLE OF WILDLIFE ON ANIMAL COMMUNITIES

There are different types of interactions wildlife experience that exists between animal species going from Parasitism (where a parasites gets benefited from host and in return kill the host) to commensalism (where one partner get benefitted other neither benefitted nor harmed). Scavengers are used for the elimination of dead animals so that diseases do not propagate to other animals and recycling of nutrients. Predators also play beneficial role in ecology by not only limit the development of potential epizootics but improvement of genetic diversity among herbivore communities (Graham *et al.*, 2005; Grizzetti *et al.*, 2019).

WILDLIFE HUNTING

It is done by specialized and non specialized hunters i.e. subsistence hunting, commercial hunting and sport hunting. Many animals are trading for medicinal uses as well as food. Many of species are banned for trade like pangolin, falcon, leopard, lion, elephant, rhino and may others (de Araujo Lima Constantino, 2016; Akrim *et*

al., 2017; MacKenzie, 2017; Perera *et al.*, 2017; Iftkhar *et al.*, 2018; Karawita *et al.*, 2018; Mahmood *et al.*, 2019; Khan *et al.*, 2020; Perera and Karawita, 2020; Waseem *et al.*, 2020; Mahmood *et al.*, 2021).

ANIMAL AS SOURCE OF ZOO NOTIC DISEASES

Human who have close connection and association with fauna in nature and captive might be at risk for “sicknesses of zoonotic”. These pathogens could be passed on from “fauna to people” and “people to people” with “vector”, “sexual contact”, “oral”, “infected droplet”, “contact”, and “aerosol”. The mutation and adaptation has driven the “co-evolution” of pathogens and fauna for many years ago. More than 1400 pathogens of human have been documented till date, out of these, “62%” have zoonotic origin (Altaf, 2020), SARS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 both are zoonotic diseases (Adil, 2021; Altaf *et al.*, 2021; Bilal *et al.*, 2021).

THREATS AND CONSERVATION

The feelings of certain radical lobbying organizations demanding severe wildlife preservation, which tends to deprive animals of any socioeconomic value, is one of the most serious threats to biodiversity. However, the debate should not become mired down in a debate about the advantages and disadvantages of sustainable wildlife use (McKinney *et al.*, 2010; Hussain *et al.*, 2015; Akrim *et al.*, 2017; Rahim *et al.*, 2018; Ijaz *et al.*, 2020). The argument between conservation and development values is futile. Conservation and development issues might intersect with a complementary strategy. The classical ideology of nature and wildlife conservation is a defensive attitude that seeks to protect nature from the effects of development, whereas modern biodiversity conservation is a voluntary approach that search for to match people's needs for ecological sources while guaranteeing the long survival of the ecological richness. This data is valuable for managers in charge of creating or altering wildlife conservation areas (Ijaz *et al.*, 2020).

REFERENCES

- Adil, S. 2021. Animals use to enhance immunity during a COVID-19 Pandemic-a mini review. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 5: 100-103.
- Adil, S., R. Kanwal, H. Aslam, S. Ijaz, S. Afsheen. 2019. Study of human impacts and interaction with herpetofauna-A review. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 3: 30-49.
- Akrim, F., T. Mahmood, R. Hussain, S. Qasim. 2017. Distribution pattern, population estimation and threats to the Indian Pangolin *Manis crassicaudata* (Mammalia: Pholidota: Manidae) in and around Pir Lasura National Park, Azad Jammu & Kashmir, Pakistan. *Journal of Threatened Taxa*. 9: 9920-9927.
- Altaf, M. 2018. Study of human-mammals conflict and interaction-A review *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 2: 20-24.
- Altaf, M. 2020. Wild animals as source of Zoonotic diseases-a review. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 4: 71-84.
- Altaf, M., T. Hussain, M.S.H. Khan, M. Umair, U. Atique, K.J. Iqbal, J. Naseer, A. Saeed, G. Yasin, M.A. Latif, R.M. Shafiq, A. Saleem, S. Adil, M.H. Hamed. 2021. An overview of Pakistan Tourism Sector, potential hindrances, and Impact of COVID-19-a review. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 5: 186-201.

- Altaf, M., S. Nazer, Musarat, I. Manzoor, B. Safeer, S. Yasrub. 2018. Study of human activities impacts and interaction with small Indian mongoose in Dhirkot, district Bagh, Azad Jammu and Kashmir. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 2: 31-37.
- Alves, R.R.N., T.P.R. Oliveira, I.L. Rosa. 2013. Wild animals used as food medicine in Brazil. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*. 2013.
- Anthony, B.P., J. Wasambo. 2009. Human-wildlife conflict study report: Vwaza Marsh Wildlife Reserve, Malawi. Central European University: Prepared for Malawi Department of National Parks and Wildlife. Budapest.
- Aslam, H., M. Faiz. 2020. Ethnopharmacological and modern applications of milk of various mammalian species-a review. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 4: 211-226.
- Babar, M., R. Kanwal. 2021. Wildlife as a bioindicator-a review *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 5: 139-145.
- Benítez, G. 2011. Animals used for medicinal and magico-religious purposes in western Granada Province, Andalusia (Spain). *Journal of ethnopharmacology*. 137: 1113-1123.
- Bilal, A., M.K. Ullah, M.S. Khan, A. Fatima, K. Iqbal, S.S. Abbasi, A. Hafeez, S. Hussain, I. Nazar. 2021. Impacts of covid-19 pandemic on wildlife-mini review. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 5: 135-138.
- Botelho, A.C., A.F. Ferreira, S.E. Fracalanza, L.M. Teixeira, T.C. Pinto. 2018. A perspective on the potential zoonotic role of *Streptococcus agalactiae*: searching for a missing link in alternative transmission routes. *Frontiers in microbiology*. 9: 608.
- Bowen-Jones, E. 2012. Tackling Human-wildlife Conflict: A prerequisite for linking conservation and poverty alleviation. *Poverty and conservation learning group discussion paper*. 6: 26.
- Burger, J. 2006a. Bioindicators: a review of their use in the environmental literature 1970–2005. *Environmental Bioindicators*. 1: 136-144.
- Burger, J. 2006b. Bioindicators: types, development, and use in ecological assessment and research. *Environmental Bioindicators*. 1: 22-39.
- da Silva, M.B., J.M. Portela, W. Li, M. Jackson, M. Gonzalez-Juarrero, A.S. Hidalgo, J.T. Belisle, R.C. Bouth, A.R. Gobbo, J.G. Barreto. 2018. Evidence of zoonotic leprosy in Pará, Brazilian Amazon, and risks associated with human contact or consumption of armadillos. *PLoS neglected tropical diseases*. 12.
- de Araujo Lima Constantino, P. 2016. Deforestation and hunting effects on wildlife across Amazonian indigenous lands. *Ecology and Society*. 21.
- EHS. 2016a. Zoonotic Diseases – Amphibians. EHS Occupational Health Clinic.
- EHS. 2016b. Zoonotic Diseases – Fish. EHS Occupational Health Clinic.
- Graham, K., A.P. Beckerman, S. Thirgood. 2005. Human–predator–prey conflicts: ecological correlates, prey losses and patterns of management. *Biological Conservation*. 122: 159-171.
- Grizzetti, B., C. Liqueste, A. Pistocchi, O. Vigiak, G. Zulian, F. Bouraoui, A. De Roo, A. Cardoso. 2019. Relationship between ecological condition and ecosystem services in European rivers, lakes and coastal waters. *Science of the Total Environment*. 671: 452-465.
- Haidar, R., S.M. Bashir. 2021. Chemical composition, traditional and modern uses of meat of animals-a review. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 5: 47-55.
- Haider, R., M. Altaf, Z. Rasheed, K. Rauf, B. Mumtaz, M. Altaf, M. Shabir, F. Hakeem, A. Iftikhar. 2017. Assessment of behavioral study, human activities impacts and interaction with white cheeked bulbul (*Pycnonotus leucotis*) in district Bagh, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. *Wildlife and Ecology*. 1: 17-24.

- Hakeem, F., M. Altaf, S. Manzoor, K. Rauf, B. Mumtaz, M. Bashir, R. Haider, S.I. Farooq, L. Safdar, M. Altaf. 2017. Assessment of behavioral study, human activities impacts and interaction with Streak laughingthrush (*Trochalopteron lineatum*) in district Bagh, Azad Jammu and Kashmir-Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 1: 1-7.
- Holt, E.A., S.W. Miller. 2011. Bioindicators: using organisms to measure environmental impacts. *Nature Education Knowledge*. 3: 8.
- Hussain, A., M. ASHRAF, M. ALTAF, W.A. KHAN, M. Akmal, J. Qazi. 2015. Relative diversity and threats to commercially important fishes of the Ravi, Pakistan. *Biologia*. 145-149.
- Iftikhar, A., M. Umair, A.R. Abbasi, S. Ashraf, S.M. Bashir, S. Afsheen, H. Aslam, S. Ijaz, S. Adil. 2018. Status and cultural uses of Indian Pangolin (*Manis crassicaudata*) in selected sites of Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 2: 23-30.
- Ijaz, S., S. Adil, H. Aslam, R. Kanwal, S. Afsheen. 2020. Human interaction, conflict, threats and role of mammals-A review. *Journal of Ethnomedicine and Ethnoecology*. 1: 1-11.
- Ijaz, S., A. Iftikhar. 2021. Chemical composition, ethnomedicinal and industrial uses of bones-a review *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 5: 56-59.
- Kanwal, R., S. Adil, H. Aslam, S. Ijaz, S. Afsheen. 2019. Human impacts and interaction with mammalian species-A review. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 3: 13-26.
- Karawita, H., P. Perera, P. Gunawardane, N. Dayawansa. 2018. Habitat preference and den characterization of Indian Pangolin (*Manis crassicaudata*) in a tropical lowland forested landscape of southwest Sri Lanka. *PloS one*. 13: e0206082.
- Kazwala, R. 2016. Zoonotic diseases at the human-domestic animal-Wildlife interface in Southern and Eastern Africa. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*. 53: 5.
- Khan, M.S.H., S. Ullah, M.H. Hamed, M. Altaf. 2020. A study of illegal wildlife trade and seizures in Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 4: 193-210.
- Liu, F., W.J. McShea, D.L. Garshelis, X. Zhu, D. Wang, L. Shao. 2011. Human-wildlife conflicts influence attitudes but not necessarily behaviors: Factors driving the poaching of bears in China. *Biological Conservation*. 144: 538-547.
- MacKenzie, J.M. 2017. *The empire of nature: Hunting, conservation and British imperialism*. Manchester University Press.
- Mahmood, T., F. Akrim, N. Irshad, R. Hussain, H. Fatima, S. Andleeb, A. Aihetasham. 2019. Distribution and illegal killing of the Endangered Indian pangolin *Manis crassicaudata* on the Potohar Plateau, Pakistan. *Oryx*. 53: 159-164.
- Mahmood, T., S. Andleeb, F. Akrim. 2021. Habitat preference of the Indian Pangolin *Manis crassicaudata* inhabiting Margalla Hills National Park, Islamabad, Pakistan. *Journal of Threatened Taxa*. 13: 18148-18155.
- McKinney, L.A., E.L. Kick, G.M. Fulkerson. 2010. World system, anthropogenic, and ecological threats to bird and mammal species: a structural equation analysis of biodiversity loss. *Organization & Environment*. 23: 3-31.
- Mughal, S., M. Pervaz, S.M. Bashir, S.S. Shamashad. 2020. Assessment of diversity and ethnopharmacological uses of birds in Chakar, Hattian Bala district, Azad Jammu and Kashmir -Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 4: 35-44.
- Muhammad, N., A.M. Khan, K.J. Iqbal, M.S. Haider, S. Ashraf, Z.S. Ansari, S.A. Chattha, A.R. Abbasi, M. Yaqoob. 2017a. Assessment of distribution and ethnocultural uses of the Baringo tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) in Punjab, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 1: 7-13.

- Muhammad, N., A.M. Khan, M. Umair, A. Qazi, A. M. Yaqoob, S. Ashraf, Q. Khan, M. Farooq. 2017b. Assessment of distribution and ethnocultural uses of the Sol (*Channa marulius*) in Punjab, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 1: 35-41.
- Muhammad, N., M. Umair, A.M. Khan, A.R. Abbasi, Q. Khan, A. Khan, M.Z. Awan. 2017c. Assessment of the diversity and ethno-medicinal uses of the carps in Punjab, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 1: 52-60.
- Nijman, V., C.R. Shepherd. 2017. Ethnozoological assessment of animals used by Mon traditional medicine vendors at Kyaiktiyo, Myanmar. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*. 206: 101-106.
- Noor, U., R. Haider. 2020. Assessment of herpetofauna diversity and human-herpetofauna-interaction in district Sudhnoti, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 4: 156-163.
- Perera, P., H. Karawita. 2020. An update of distribution, habitats and conservation status of the Indian pangolin (*Manis crassicaudata*) in Sri Lanka. *Global Ecology and Conservation*. 21: e00799.
- Perera, P., K. Karawita, M. Pabasara. 2017. Pangolins *Manis crassicaudata* in Sri Lanka A Review of Current Knowledge Threats and Research Priorities.
- Pradhan, A., P. Bhaumik, S. Das, M. Mishra, S. Khanam, B.A. Hoque, I. Mukherjee, A.R. Thakur, S.R. Chaudhuri. 2008. Phytoplankton diversity as indicator of water quality for fish cultivation.
- Rahim, A., K. Gabol, W. Ahmed, B. Manzoor, A. Batool. 2018. Population assessment, threats and conservation measures of marsh crocodile at Dasht River, Gwadar. *Pakistan Journal of Marine Sciences*. 27: 45-53.
- Rauf, K., M. Altaf, B. Mumtaz, M. Altaf, R. Haider, B. Safeer, S.I. Farooq, L. Safdar, M. Manzoor, S. Yasrub, S.M. Bashir, A. Iftikhar. 2017. Assessment of behavior, distribution, ecology and interaction study of Cinnamon Tree Sparrow (*Passer rutilans*) in district Bagh-Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 1: 43-49.
- Saeed, A., M. Umair, M. Altaf, T. Hussain, A.M. Abbasi. 2022. Ethno-veterinary medicines of South Punjab, Pakistan *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 6: 64-81.
- Saleem, R., M. Altaf, M. Umair, M.S. Amjad, A.M. Abbasi. 2021. Ethnopharmacological applications of the amphibians and reptiles among the people in the vicinity of Margalla Hill National Park, Islamabad, Pakistan. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 5: 13-25.
- Shiferaw, M.L., J.B. Doty, G. Maghlakelidze, J. Morgan, E. Khmaladze, O. Parkadze, M. Donduashvili, E.O. Wemakoy, J.-J. Muyembe, L. Mulumba. 2017. Frameworks for preventing, detecting, and controlling zoonotic diseases. *Emerging infectious diseases*. 23: S71.
- Sidra, S., R. Saleem, S. Ghafoor, H. Azeem, I. Imtiaz, Z. Parveen. 2019. Fecal matter as a bio-indicator tool for heavy metal pollution. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 3: 1-7.
- Sreekeesoon, D.P., M.F. Mahomoodally. 2014. Ethnopharmacological analysis of medicinal plants and animals used in the treatment and management of pain in Mauritius. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*. 157: 181-200.
- Thakur, R., R. Jindal, U.B. Singh, A. Ahluwalia. 2013. Plankton diversity and water quality assessment of three freshwater lakes of Mandi (Himachal Pradesh, India) with special reference to planktonic indicators. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*. 185: 8355-8373.
- Umair, M., D. Sinha, M. Haasan. 2022. Ethnopharmacological uses of animals and plants in cancer treatment-a review. *Journal of Wildlife and Ecology*. 2: 32-47.

- Vijayakumar, S., J.M. Yabesh, S. Prabhu, M. Ayyanar, R. Damodaran. 2015. Ethnozoological study of animals used by traditional healers in Silent Valley of Kerala, India. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*. 162: 296-305.
- Waseem, M., B. Khan, T. Mahmood, H.S. Hussain, R. Aziz, F. Akrim, T. Ahmad, R. Nazir, M.W. Ali, M.N. Awan. 2020. Occupancy, habitat suitability and habitat preference of endangered indian pangolin (*Manis crassicaudata*) in Potohar Plateau and Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. *Global Ecology and Conservation*. 23: e01135.
- Ye, Z.-W., S. Yuan, K.-S. Yuen, S.-Y. Fung, C.-P. Chan, D.-Y. Jin. 2020. Zoonotic origins of human coronaviruses. *Int J Biol Sci*. 16: 1686-1697.
- Yirga, G., M. Teferi, Y. Gebreslassea. 2011. Ethnozoological study of traditional medicinal animals used by the people of Kafta-Humera District, Northern Ethiopia. *International Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences*. 3: 316-320.